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Gap analysis on the implementation of reference genomes and genomics in conservation, bioeconomy and disease applications

Intermediate report

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João Pimenta [CIBIO-BIOPOLIS]

José Melo-Ferreira [CIBIO-BIOPOLIS]

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Executive Summary

Integrated in the T11.3, this gap analysis offers a snapshot of the current state of genomic applications across conservation, bioeconomy, and disease management. Through an extensive literature review, 1000 research articles were analysed in detail to assess the use of reference genomes and genomics for the development of practical field applications. These applications can and are being used by practitioners and non-scientist to make assessments of population and stock status, and disease prevention. High throughput technologies are increasingly being used to develop new applications in biodiversity, while low throughput methods remain relevant for traditional genetic diversity studies. The Gap Analysis also explores the inequalities of access to funds, expertise and infrastructure between developed and under-development countries around the world and within the European Union. Overall, this Gap Analysis tackled the issues hindering the capacity to apply genomics and reference genomes for the protection of biodiversity, trying to point solution to overcome these problems and expand the use of genomics in the field for the protection of biodiversity.

Keywords

Gap analysis, genomics, reference genomes, applications, inequalities

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List of abbreviation (adjust as needed)

CA	Consortium Agreement
D	Deliverable
DMP	Data Management Plan
EB	Executive Board
EEAB	External Experts Advisory Board
GA	General Assembly
M	Milestone
PA	Project Administrator
PL	Pillar Leader
PMT	Project Management Team
PM	Project Manager
SL	Stream Leader
SOPs	Standards Operational Procedures
WPL	Working Package Leader

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1. Objectives and purpose

1.1. Introduction

Human activities are causing an unprecedented biodiversity crisis on our planet, with species extinction rates accelerating due to a combination of habitat destruction, climate change, pollution, and unsustainable resource exploitation. These threats are undermining the stability of ecosystems and the essential services they provide to human societies. Tackling this crisis requires advanced scientific methodologies, and genomics has emerged as a pivotal tool in this endeavour. Recent breakthroughs in genomic research have deepened our understanding of evolutionary relationships, genetic diversity, and species adaptation, presenting new opportunities for biodiversity management in the fields of conservation, bioeconomy and disease prevention.

Genomic technologies, particularly the use of reference genomes, have transformed the way scientists study genetic variation within and among species. These resources are fundamental for detecting genetic markers associated with resilience, adaptation, and population viability. By offering precise insights into population structures, gene flow, and species health, genomics provides essential data for designing effective conservation strategies. Despite these advances, the integration of genomic data into applications remains relatively limited due to technical, economic, and logistical barriers.

This analysis seeks to assess the current state of genomic applications in biodiversity science, pinpoint existing limitations, and propose solutions to enhance the transition from basic genomic research to applied conservation practices. A systematic review of literature will examine how genomics and reference genomes have been utilized in biodiversity protection efforts and identify obstacles preventing their broader implementation.

Beyond technical constraints, socio-economic disparities and infrastructural limitations pose significant challenges to the widespread adoption of genomic technologies. Constraints such as limited funding, insufficient expertise, and the complexity of genomic analyses create barriers to accessibility. To ensure that genomic research translates into actionable conservation strategies, it is critical to enhance the availability of genomic resources and know-how for biodiversity practitioners. Broadening access to reference genomes and genomic tools will facilitate improved policies and species management plans, ultimately supporting biodiversity resilience. Therefore, strengthening international cooperation and

investing in shared research infrastructure are essential steps toward fostering equitable access to genomic innovations.

1.2. Objective

This gap analysis will highlight critical areas for development in conservation genomics, disease management, and bioeconomy applications. By identifying barriers and potential solutions, this study aims to enhance the practical application of genomics in biodiversity conservation. Addressing both scientific and socio-economic challenges will facilitate a more seamless integration of genomic advancements into conservation practice, ensuring the sustainability of ecosystems in a rapidly changing world.

2. Methodology

2.1. Rules and guidelines for literature mining

The Standard Operating Procedure for the Gap analysis was developed with intends to establish a common strategy with T11.4 and a common procedure for literature mining, metadata analysis, and information gathering within the scope of the three following perspectives: From Basic to Applied Science, Inequalities and Communication gaps between “interested parties” (from scientists to stakeholders), and From Applied Science to Stakeholders engagement.

To ensure the robustness and relevance of our Gap Analysis development we have identified Pubmed (<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/advanced/>) as the suitable database for conducting our literature search.

The methodology for the literature mining and review is described in the Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) for the Gap Analysis and in the M11.3 milestone. The SOP was created to ensure uniformity in the research article evaluation by the reviewing team. The literature review was design to have two stages of evaluation. The first contemplated the evaluation of all research articles, and the full detail information was retrieved from those deem to have a claim of application and using empirical data. Following the first review, the coordination and reviewing teams met to discuss the evaluation process, concluding that several fields should change their structure to improve the quality of the data retrieved by the reviewing team. A new version of the SOP was created and made available to the team. The research articles passing the first stage of the evaluation, were redistributed to the team for a second round of evaluations, to confirm the data retrieved in the first phase and update the new or improved categories.

2.2. 2nd review process – genomics and applications

The second phase of the literature review process focusing on the use of genomics and reference genomes for application development included changes in several fields to improve the quality of the information, following the suggestions of the reviewing team. Here we include

a summary of the changes made. For more details check the latest version of the SOP for the Gap Analysis.

2.2.1 Summary of the changes in the SOP for the genomics and application section

- **Collecting countries of affiliation of the first and last authors.** All countries of affiliation of the first and last authors were retrieved.
- **Collecting taxonomic groups.** The number of taxonomic groups was increased to accommodate a larger number of organisms.

Table 1. List of the taxonomic groups considerer for the literature review

Taxonomic Group	Species examples
Viruses	Tobacco mosaic virus (TMV), Human immunodeficiency virus (HIV), Influenza A virus
Bacteria	Escherichia coli, Staphylococcus aureus, Bacillus subtilis
Protist	Plasmodium falciparum, Paramecium caudatum, Amoeba proteus
Mammalia	Homo sapiens, Panthera leo, Canis lupus
Birds	Corvus corax, Spheniscus demersus, Struthio camelus
Reptilia	Chelonia mydas, Python regius, Crocodylus niloticus
Amphibia	Rana catesbeiana, Ambystoma mexicanum, Dendrobates tinctorius
Fish	Danio rerio, Oncorhynchus mykiss, Salmo salar

Insecta	<i>Drosophila melanogaster</i> , <i>Apis mellifera</i> , <i>Coccinella septempunctata</i>
Arachnida	<i>Latrodectus mactans</i> , <i>Loxosceles reclusa</i> , <i>Aphonopelma chalcodes</i>
Crustacea	<i>Homarus americanus</i> , <i>Procambarus clarkii</i> , <i>Carcinus maenas</i>
Fungi	<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> , <i>Agaricus bisporus</i> , <i>Penicillium chrysogenum</i>
Sponges	<i>Spongilla lacustris</i> , <i>Euplectella aspergillum</i> , <i>Sycon ciliatum</i>
Cnidaria	<i>Aurelia aurita</i> , <i>Nematostella vectensis</i> , <i>Acropora palmata</i>
Mollusk	<i>Octopus vulgaris</i> , <i>Helix pomatia</i> , <i>Mytilus edulis</i>
Annelida	<i>Lumbricus terrestris</i> , <i>Hirudo medicinalis</i> , <i>Nereis virens</i>
Nematoda	<i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i> , <i>Ascaris lumbricoides</i> , <i>Trichinella spiralis</i>
Echinodermata	<i>Asterias rubens</i> , <i>Strongylocentrotus purpuratus</i> , <i>Holothuria edulis</i>
Angiosperms	<i>Rosa rubiginosa</i> , <i>Zea mays</i> , <i>Quercus robur</i>
Gymnosperms	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i> , <i>Ginkgo biloba</i> , <i>Sequoia sempervirens</i>
Ferns and Horsetails	<i>Pteridium aquilinum</i> , <i>Equisetum arvense</i> , <i>Polypodium vulgare</i>
Club Mosses	<i>Lycopodium clavatum</i> , <i>Huperzia selago</i> , <i>Selaginella kraussiana</i>
Mosses	<i>Sphagnum palustre</i> , <i>Polytrichum commune</i> , <i>Bryum argenteum</i>
Liverworts	<i>Marchantia polymorpha</i> , <i>Conocephalum conicum</i> , <i>Riccia fluitans</i>

Hornworts	Anthoceros agrestis, Phaeoceros carolinianus, Dendroceros crispus
Green Algae	Chlamydomonas reinhardtii, Volvox aureus, Ulva lactuca
Brown Algae	Fucus vesiculosus, Macrocystis pyrifera, Sargassum muticum
Red Algae	Porphyra umbilicalis, Gracilaria verrucosa, Chondrus crispus

- **High-throughput genetic data.** The list of categories of data used in the research articles was updated to include more types of data.
- **Low-throughput genetic data.** The list of categories of data used in the research articles was updated to include more types of data.
- **New or published data.** This was a new field included in the SOP, to obtain the information on if the empirical data used the research article was new or obtain previously.
- **Which genetic metrics are employed.** Based on the most common metrics included by the reviewers during the first phase, an updated version of this field was created to include more metrics and summary statistics.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Results from the literature mining

The literature mining resulted in a final database of 10241 research articles to be revised. The findings reported here are based on 1000 papers reviewed following the newest version of the SOP. Note that the reported results are still preliminary because the second review did not yet finish.

3.2. The fast-growing use of genomics

To evaluate the historical trend of scientific publication addressing biodiversity applications, we investigated the number of publish manuscripts over the last four decades. The number of papers claiming a biodiversity-related application remained negligible until the 1990s. A gradual increase was observed afterward, with a significant surge in publications after the early 2000s. The number of papers peaked in the last couple of years (Fig1A).

When comparing high-throughput (HT) data and low-throughput (LT) data reveals a distinct trend over time (Fig.1B). Before the year 2010, almost all biodiversity-related studies relied on LT methods. While LT-based studies continued to grow steadily, the rise in HT genomic studies became more prominent after 2010, with a sharp increase from 2015 onwards. By 2020, the number of HT-based studies approached the number of LT-based studies. This shift shows the increasing reliance on genomic technologies in biodiversity research.

The increasing use of high-throughput genomic data represents a major advancement in biodiversity research. Unlike traditional low-throughput methods, which focus on a limited number of genetic markers, HT genomic approaches provide a much more comprehensive view of genetic diversity, adaptation, and evolutionary processes. This shift has the potential to have profound implications for biodiversity conservation, species management, and ecological research.

One of the key advantages of HT genomic technologies is their ability to capture genetic variation at a much higher resolution. It allows researchers to analyse thousands to millions of genetic markers across entire genomes, providing deeper insights into population structure, gene flow, and evolutionary adaptation. This level of detail is particularly valuable for identifying genetic adaptive variants, which are critical to device conservation measures.

Figure 1. Publication trend of research articles claiming the development of application in biodiversity over time. a) Publication trend of research articles claiming the development of an application in biodiversity in the last four decades. b) Publication trend of research articles claiming the development of an application in biodiversity using high-throughput (in red) and low-throughput data (in green).

3.3 Significant countries disparities in applied research

The recent world's country classification by the UN Trade and Development (UNCTAD), divides the countries into Global North and Global South. This classification takes in consideration socioeconomical and political aspects of the country development. Overall, Global South refers to countries from Africa, Latin America, Caribbean, Asia (excluding Japan, South Korea and Israel) and Oceania (excluding Australia and New Zealand). The comparison of the research output between the Global North (~67%, n=673) and Global South (~32%, n=321) reveals a stark imbalance, with the Global North contributing the majority of scientific publications (Fig2ab). The United States is the most prolific contributor, accounting for 19% of the total research output in our dataset. The Global South has a notably lower representation in scientific publications. A chi-square test confirmed that this difference in research productivity is statistically significant ($p\text{-value} < 2.2e\text{-}16$), indicating that the observed disparity is not due to random variation but rather reflects deeper structural differences in research funding, institutional capacity, and access to resources.

A similar trend is observed when comparing Widening vs. Strengthening countries within the European Union (Fig2cd). Strengthening countries, such as Germany, France, the Netherlands, Sweden, and Denmark, have historically strong research infrastructures, well-funded academic institutions, and greater access to competitive EU grants. In contrast, Widening countries, such as Poland, Portugal, Bulgaria, Romania, and Croatia, produce significantly fewer publications. A chi-square test also confirmed a significant difference in research output between these two groups ($p\text{-value} < 2.2e\text{-}16$), reinforcing the current divergence within the European research ecosystem. While some Widening countries, like Poland and Portugal, contribute a higher share compared to others, their overall representation (n=50) remains lower than that of Strengthening countries (n=189). The pie charts highlight that research output in Widening countries is fragmented, with a long tail of countries producing only a very small number of research outputs.

These findings emphasize the economic, infrastructural, and systemic inequalities that shape scientific output worldwide. The Global North benefits from strong academic institutions, well-established funding mechanisms, and advanced technological infrastructure, allowing them to lead scientific research. The Global South, by contrast, faces numerous challenges, including limited financial support for research, inadequate laboratory facilities, and reduced access to

international collaboration opportunities. As a result, the scientific contributions from Global South nations remain disproportionately lower, perpetuating global inequalities in knowledge production. Addressing these disparities requires targeted funding initiatives, increased collaboration between Global North and Global South institutions, and policies that support research capacity-building in underrepresented regions.

Figure 2. Publication imbalances between world and European Union countries. a) Publication rates of global north countries; the five most prolific countries are highlighted. b) Publication rates of global south countries; the five most prolific countries are highlighted. c) Publication rates for Strengthening countries in the European Union. d) Publication rates for Widening countries in the European Union. Below each plot we detailed the number of research articles in our dataset attributed to each group of countries.

Similarly, the gap between Widening and Strengthening countries within Europe reflects historical and economic differences in national investments in research and development (Fig2cd). Strengthening countries (~79% of the research output) have long benefited from robust academic networks and easier access to competitive funding, while Widening countries often struggle with bureaucratic hurdles, lower research budgets, and difficulties in attracting and retaining top scientists. If the European Union aims to create a more balanced and integrated research landscape, it must provide greater support for Widening countries through initiatives such as targeted funding programs, research infrastructure improvements, and training opportunities. Strengthening collaboration between Widening and Strengthening countries could also help bridge the gap, fostering a more inclusive European research community.

3.4 Applied research is mainly focused on conservation

For this Gap Analysis, we explore the development of applications in the fields of conservation, bioeconomy and disease prevention. Being able to categorise the research articles allow us to identify key priorities in genomic research and understand how scientific efforts are distributed across different fields. Our results show that the distribution of studies across conservation, bioeconomy, and disease reveals clear differences in research focus (Fig3a). Conservation-related studies dominate, with 520 studies exclusively dedicated to conservation and an additional 111 studies overlapping with bioeconomy and disease. In contrast, disease-related research accounts for 225 standalone studies, with 42 studies overlapping with bioeconomy and only 19 overlapping with conservation. Bioeconomy has the fewest independent studies, with only 79 focusing exclusively on this topic, while a single study integrates all three categories. The overwhelming dominance of conservation-related research reflects the urgency of biodiversity loss and species management as major scientific priorities. The relatively lower number of bioeconomy-related studies suggests that genomic applications in sustainable industries, resource management, and biotechnology remain underexplored compared to conservation efforts. Disease research, while substantial, is more concentrated in specific taxonomic groups, reflecting the nature of pathogen-host interactions and public health concerns.

When looking at the taxonomic groups, our results highlight significant disparities in focus across different groups (Fig3b). Angiosperms (flowering plants), mammals, and fish are the most frequently studied groups across all categories, particularly in conservation. In contrast, bacteria, archaeobacteria, and viruses are predominantly studied in disease contexts. Conservation research is largely centred on angiosperms, with 195 studies focusing on their ecological significance and role in ecosystem functioning. Mammals (142 studies) and fish (88 studies) also receive significant attention, aligning with conservation efforts targeting iconic species and commercially important biodiversity. Other groups such as birds (56 studies), reptiles (20 studies), amphibians (19 studies), and crustaceans (19 studies) also show moderate representation, reflecting their ecological and economical importance or vulnerability.

Figure 3. Research field and taxonomic categorisation of the research articles. a) Venn diagram showing the distribution of research articles across the three study categories: conservation (green), bioeconomy (blue), and disease (red). The diagram illustrates the number of studies exclusively focused on each category, as well as those that overlap between two or all three categories. The intersections represent studies that address multiple research areas simultaneously. b) Barplot showing the number of research articles per taxonomic group, categorized by study focus: conservation (green), bioeconomy (blue), and disease (red). Bars represent the total number of studies for each taxonomic group, with different colors indicating the proportion of studies dedicated to each category. Taxonomic groups are ordered from the most to the least studied.

On the other hand, disease research is dominated by studies on viruses (54 studies), bacteria and archaea (84 studies), and protists (48 studies). These groups include many pathogens that impact human, animal, and plant health, making them a priority for disease-focused genomic studies. Other taxonomic groups associated with disease research include fungi (25 studies), nematodes (7 studies), and insects (27 studies), likely due to their roles as pathogens, parasites, or vectors.

Bioeconomy research is more limited overall, with angiosperms (78 studies) and fish (40 studies) emerging as the most frequently studied taxonomic groups. This trend is expected given the importance of plants in agriculture, forestry, and pharmaceuticals, and fish as a food resource. Other notable groups in bioeconomy research include bacteria and archaea (18 studies), fungi (14 studies), and mammals (12 studies), reflecting their applications in biotechnology, medicine, and food. The relatively low number of studies in bioeconomy suggests that the economic potential of many taxonomic groups remains underexplored in genomic research, particularly compared to conservation and disease-focused studies.

Overall, our results underscore the different priorities driving genomic research across biological domains. Conservation studies focus on protecting biodiversity and often target iconic or ecologically significant species like mammals, birds, and plants. Disease research, in contrast, concentrates on pathogenic organisms, including microbes and viruses, which have direct health implications for humans and wildlife. On the other hand, bioeconomy research remains relatively limited, suggesting that genomic applications in economic sectors, such as sustainable fisheries, forestry, and agriculture, may require further investment. One striking observation is that for certain taxonomic groups, research is heavily skewed towards one category (Fig3b). For example, viruses, bacteria, and protists are primarily studied in the context of disease, with almost no focus on conservation or bioeconomy. In opposition, many plant and vertebrate species receive extensive conservation-focused research but little attention in disease or bioeconomy contexts. These biases reflect both the inherent characteristics of the taxa, such as viruses being predominantly pathogenic, and research funding priorities, such as conservation grants targeting large mammals and ecosystem services.

In summary, these results highlight imbalances in research focus that could have long-term implications for biodiversity management, public health, and sustainable development. Increasing research in underrepresented areas, such as bioeconomic applications of microbial diversity or disease monitoring in conservation, could help bridge existing gaps and create a more comprehensive understanding of how genomics can be applied to address pressing scientific and societal challenges. Tackling these imbalances through targeted funding, interdisciplinary research, and policy initiatives could enhance the overall impact of genomics and its contributions to both conservation and applied sciences.

3.5 The use of high-throughput data and reference genomes in applied research is still limited

The increasing accessibility of genomic technologies has expanded our capacity to address challenges across various biological and ecological research fields. Low throughput and high throughput sequencing methods offer distinct advantages and challenges depending on the research context, species studied, and available resources. High throughput technologies (e.g., whole-genome sequencing, transcriptomics, and SNP arrays) provide large-scale genomic insights that are crucial for evolutionary studies, population genetics, and conservation genomics. In contrast, low throughput approaches (e.g., microsatellites, AFLP, Sanger sequencing, and qPCR) are often more cost-effective and targeted, making them valuable for species with limited genomic resources. Comparing the use of these two data types is essential for understanding current trends in genomic research, assessing methodological gaps, and identifying opportunities for improving data integration.

A Venn diagram comparing the use of high and low throughput data reveals distinct research preferences (Fig4a). While some of the studies exclusively rely on high throughput genetic data for more comprehensive characterization of populations and species, most of the research use low throughput genetic data, such as microsatellites (STR) and sanger sequencing. Only a very small number of papers have used both types of data, suggesting a limited integration of these approaches, which could otherwise be used to validate findings, cross-compare genetic markers, or bridge the gap between traditional and modern sequencing techniques.

Figure 4. The use of low and high throughput data and reference genomes in applied research. a) Venn diagram of the number of studies using low (red) or high (blue) throughput data. In darkblue is highlighted the number of studies using both types of data. b) Half donuts plots of the percentages of

studies using new data and/or published data. c) Barplot of the most frequently genetic markers used in low throughput studies. d) Barplot of the most frequently genetic markers used in high throughput studies. e) Percentage of low throughput studies using reference genome to analyse the genetic data. f) Percentage of high throughput studies using reference genomes to analyse the genomic data.

Our results also showed that most of the research is developed using newly produced data for both low and high throughput (Fig4b). However, 36% of the research articles using high throughput data rely on published data. This trend highlights the increasing role of data reusability and accessibility in genomic research. In contrast, low throughput studies are more likely to generate new data (75.2%) rather than rely on previously published datasets (24.4%), likely due to the targeted nature of these methodologies. Nevertheless, the combination of both new and published data in some studies suggests that hybrid approaches are likely being employed to maximize analytical power.

A comparison of the types of data used in high and low throughput research reveals remarkable differences (Fig4cd). While low throughput studies rely heavily on classical markers such as Short Tandem Repeats (STRs) and sanger sequencing, which remain effective for species with limited genomic resources, high throughput studies usually employ a more diverse type of data, e.g. whole-genome sequencing, transcriptomics, RAD sequency or SNP arrays, genotyping-by-sequencing, and transcriptomics.

The analysis of reference genome usage further highlights the disparities between high and low throughput studies (Fig4ef). High throughput research is significantly more likely to incorporate reference genomes, particularly at chromosome-level assemblies (qui-square test, p value $< 2.2e-16$). This is expected, as whole-genome sequencing and SNP-based approaches require well-annotated reference genomes for accurate read alignment and variant calling. Low throughput studies show a lower reliance on reference genomes, likely due to their use of markers that do not require whole-genome context, such as microsatellites and targeted PCR-based assays. Despite the higher proportion of reference genome use in high throughput studies, many studies still rely on draft or fragmented assemblies rather than chromosome-level assemblies (Fig4f). This may be due to gaps in genome completeness, lack of reference genomes for non-model species, or challenges in assembling large or complex genomes.

The comparison between the use of low and high throughput sequencing in the development of applications in biodiversity provides relevant insights into methodological choices, reference genome usage, and data availability in genomic research. While, high throughput methods dominate large-scale genomic studies and often require high-quality reference genomes, low throughput techniques remain essential for targeted, cost-effective genetic analyses. However, the availability of well-assembled reference genomes remains a bottleneck for many studies, particularly in non-model organisms. These findings emphasize the need for continued investment in reference genome projects and improved accessibility to sequencing technologies, particularly for researchers working in biodiversity conservation, evolutionary genetics, and applied genomic fields.

3.6 Remarkable differences in genetic metrics trends between low and high throughput data

Genetic diversity analysis plays a crucial role in understanding evolutionary processes, population structure, and the adaptive potential of species. Advances in sequencing technologies have dramatically transformed the field, enabling researchers to produce large amounts of data that facilitate the use of more sophisticated and comprehensive genetic metrics. However, studies employing low throughput methods remain relevant, particularly when focusing on classical population genetic methods. Thus, understanding the differences in the utilization of genetic metrics between high and low throughput studies is essential for interpreting research trends and methodological choices in population genetics and evolutionary biology.

Barplots comparing the top 10 genetic metrics used for high and low throughput research articles reveal contrasting trends. Low throughput studies predominantly rely on simpler population genetic metrics such as Allele Frequency and Heterozygosity, which are easier to estimate with smaller datasets (Fig5a). Methods like AMOVA and Nei's distance are also frequently used, indicating that low throughput studies remain focused on traditional population structure and genetic diversity estimations. Contrastingly, high throughput studies tend to employ more sophisticated metrics that require larger datasets, such as Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Structure Assignment (Fig5b). Additionally, high throughput methods also commonly use genetic diversity measures like Nucleotide Diversity and Wright's

F-statistics (FIS, FST, and FIT). This suggests that high throughput studies are more frequently aimed at comprehensive population structure analyses and understanding fine-scale genetic patterns within species. This contrast between high and low throughput studies underscores the continued relevance of classical metrics in studies where high throughput technologies may be less accessible or necessary, while demonstrating the importance of complex methods using high throughput data for a comprehensive understanding of the genetic landscape of populations and species.

Figure 5. Genetic Metric Utilization, genetic material trends and application development. a) Genetic metrics frequently employed using low throughput data. b) Most frequent genetic metrics used for high throughput data. c) Venn diagram of usage of various types of genetic material (Nuclear DNA, mtDNA, cpDNA, and Virus DNA) and their combinations across studies, with intersection sizes indicating the number of studies employing specific combinations. d) Pie chart of the proportion of

studies reporting practical applications arising from their research, without the necessity of further research.

We also estimated a Venn diagram detailing the use of different genetic materials across the studies (Fig5c). Results indicate that Nuclear DNA is by far the most commonly used genetic material, appearing in 724 studies, including 519 where it was the only material analysed. Mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) is also commonly used, featuring in 281 studies, while Virus DNA appears in 148 studies. Chloroplast DNA (cpDNA) is much less frequently used, with only 51 studies reporting its use. Combinations of genetic materials are also evident, with a total of 212 studies including more than one type of material. The pairing of Nuclear DNA and mtDNA being the most frequent combination, appearing in 148 studies. Notably, only 13 studies employ 3 types of genetic material. Overall, the results emphasize the dominance of Nuclear DNA in genomic applications. Expanding the use of combined genetic materials could provide a more holistic understanding of genetic variation, especially in plants and mixed-species ecosystems. Future research should explore ways to facilitate the integration of multiple genetic markers, potentially through improved bioinformatics tools and more standardized methodologies.

Finally, we evaluated if an actual application resulted from the research developed in each study. Note that, as detailed in the Gap Analysis SOP, an application is defined as “*An application toolkit for genomics in the field of conservation, bioeconomy, and disease is a comprehensive set of tools, knowledge, resources, and protocols specifically tailored for the application of genomic strategies and methods by practitioners and non-scientists*” without the necessity of any further research. Our results show that almost a fifth of the studies claiming the development of an application were unable to demonstrate the practical application of their results. Nevertheless, most of the studies were deemed to develop a genetic or genomic application, demonstrating the growing awareness of the importance of applied research for the protection of earth’s biodiversity.

4. General Conclusions and Recommendations

The increasing use of high-throughput sequencing technologies has significantly transformed biodiversity research, providing deeper insights into genetic diversity, population structure,

and evolutionary processes. However, low-throughput methods remain widely used, particularly in studies where resources are limited or where traditional genetic diversity estimates are sufficient for research objectives. The comparison between high and low-throughput studies demonstrates that high-throughput research tends to employ more computationally demanding metrics, while low-throughput studies continue to rely on classical population genetics approaches. Despite these methodological differences, both approaches remain essential, and the integration of multiple techniques could enhance genomic research by combining the strengths of both strategies.

Genomic research is predominantly focused on conservation, with far fewer studies addressing bioeconomy and disease-related applications. This suggests that conservation priorities have historically shaped genomic research funding, while bioeconomic applications—such as genomics for sustainable agriculture, forestry, and industrial biotechnology—remain comparatively underexplored. Likewise, disease-focused genomic research is concentrated in specific taxa, primarily viruses, bacteria, and protists, with limited integration of conservation and bioeconomic perspectives. Additionally, taxonomic biases are evident, with mammals, fish, and angiosperms (flowering plants) being the most studied groups, while microorganisms, invertebrates, and non-flowering plants receive much less attention. This imbalance highlights the need for broader research efforts targeting underrepresented taxa to ensure a more comprehensive application of genomic tools across biodiversity.

The analysis of genetic material usage reveals a strong reliance on Nuclear DNA across studies, with far fewer incorporating mitochondrial (mtDNA) or chloroplast (cpDNA) DNA. The underrepresentation of cpDNA suggests a gap in plant genetic studies, while the limited number of studies utilizing multiple genetic materials indicates that integrative approaches remain underexplored. Expanding the use of combined genetic markers would allow for a more comprehensive understanding of genetic diversity and evolutionary processes, particularly for non-model organisms where reference genomes are still lacking.

Results further highlight the disparity between fundamental research and the development of practical genomic applications. Although many studies claim to develop applications, nearly a fifth of them lack clear evidence of practical implementation. This suggests that genomic research is still largely exploratory, with limited translation into real-world conservation strategies, bioeconomic innovations, or disease management tools. Strengthening the connection between research and application will require improved frameworks for

implementation, greater interdisciplinary collaboration, and stronger engagement with practitioners and stakeholders to ensure that genomic data is effectively utilized in decision-making.

A major issue identified in this study is the significant inequality in genomic research output between countries. The Global North dominates research in this field, while the Global South remains considerably underrepresented. A similar pattern is observed within Europe, where Strengthening countries contribute the majority of genomic research, while Widening countries produce far fewer studies. This imbalance is largely due to disparities in funding, access to sequencing technologies, and differences in research infrastructure. Without targeted efforts to address these inequalities, gaps in genomic research will persist, limiting the capacity of certain regions to leverage genomic data for conservation, economic development and disease prevention.

To address these challenges, it is essential to promote the accessibility of high-throughput technologies by increasing investments in sequencing infrastructure and bioinformatics training, particularly in underrepresented regions. Expanding the availability of high-quality reference genomes, especially for non-model species, will improve the accuracy of genomic analyses and broaden their applications in conservation, bioeconomy, and disease research. Encouraging interdisciplinary and multi-marker approaches will provide more comprehensive insights into genetic diversity and enhance the resolution of genomic studies. Also, strengthening collaboration between researchers, policymakers, and practitioners, across several countries, will be key to bridging the gap between fundamental research and its application in real-world scenarios. Finally, addressing geographical disparities in genomic research requires targeted funding programs, infrastructure improvements, and training initiatives to support equitable access to genomic technologies.

By tackling these issues, genomic research can be more effectively integrated into conservation, sustainable resource management, and disease prevention efforts. Ensuring broader accessibility to genomic tools and fostering inclusive research initiatives will maximize the societal and environmental benefits of genomics, ultimately contributing to the preservation of biodiversity and the development of innovative applications in bioeconomy and public health.

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